

Discover open linked research.

FACTSHEET FOR RESOURCE MANAGERS, RESEARCHERS AND RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

What is EXPLORE?

OpenAIRE EXPLORE is an open research discovery portal providing access to millions of interlinked scholarly works (publications, data, software), their related research products and contextual information such as organisations and grants.

It is built on top of the OpenAIRE Graph one of the largest open scholarly record collections, with integrated content from more than 12K trusted data sources worldwide.

Our target

OpenAIRE EXPLORE is mainly targeted for researchers, offering services to help them to find ways to enhance and share research.

Linked to a trusted OpenAIRE authentication and authorization service and by using its own institutional or personal ORCID account, researchers can claim research products (e.g., link publications or datasets to specific grants or research communities, datasets to publications) and enrich their project, research community or personal research portfolio.

Main features

Search and **advanced search** research products, projects, data sources and organisations by:

- Using filters to narrow down the search results.
- Viewing the connections between the results in a detailed page.

Link your **research products** with your community, funding, and other research products.

- Find your research either within OpenAIRE or reach out to external sources via **APIs**.

Add to ORCID your research products with the **ORCID search and link wizard**.

- The linked works instantly appear in your ORCID record page too.

Find statistics, metrics and graphs

- For projects, data sources, and research products.

Download

- Reports for research products of projects, organisations, and data sources.
- Search results.

Browse pages for Fields of Science (FoS) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

- Access thematically and discover research more effectively.

Deposit

- Find an OpenAIRE compatible repository to deposit your research products.
- Select an OpenAIRE compatible repository so that your research is linked to your funding information.

View all Funders indexed in OpenAIRE

EXPLORE

Starting from the **search functionality**, researchers can easily discover the research products they are interested in, by applying **filters and keywords** on the OpenAIRE Graph's contents.

In the detailed pages of the research products, researchers can find useful information such as:

- connections with all its interlinked data,
- other related research products,
- projects and funding,
- research communities and subjects of interest.

Indicator-based metrics for usage such as **views and downloads**, impact-based metrics such as **popularity and influence**, **research statistical analysis and graphs** are also available to the users.

The **linking functionality** and the **ORCID Search and Link Wizard** offer users the flexibility of **building their own portfolio in OpenAIRE EXPLORE**, but also become an integral part of the OpenAIRE Graph by contributing to its continuous enhancement.

OpenAIRE Explore **supports research in the publishing phase** too, because researchers can browse the available repositories and find the most suitable for publishing their research outputs. In case there is no specific repository for a user, it is always suggested to use **OpenAIRE's catch all repository, Zenodo** (<https://zenodo.org/>).

In the **new Funders page** you can view all funders indexed in OpenAIRE together with the keys details about each funder.

Main benefits

→ Eliminate the effort of aggregating and reporting

Publish in **open access** (OA) and use the Embed results functionality of OpenAIRE EXPLORE to include your project's research products in your website. Automatically retrieve results to the EC portal for reporting.

→ Use one platform for your discovery needs

Discover and navigate across publications, data, software and other research products. From trusted sources around the world.

→ Increase visibility & impact of your work

Find where to deposit and meet **OA mandates**. Get your work indexed and reachable to a worldwide audience.

→ Access and link your research all in one place

Create your own portfolio of your research products and interlink them with other research products, projects or research communities.

Did you know that you may...

→ use EXPLORE as an application platform as a service (aPaaS) and set up a national portal for Open Science, such as **Canada.EXPLORE?** Find out here - <https://canada.explore.openaire.eu/>

→ have your repository, Journal or CRIS system indexed in EXPLORE and take advantage of services for enriching metadata and counting usage? Know more - <https://provide.openaire.eu>

About OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu

Shifting scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research.

For more information, please contact: helpdesk@openaire.eu

Webinars & public presentations about EXPLORE

<https://www.openaire.eu/tag/webinars/openaire-explore-webinars>

Follow EXPLORE planned actions in Trello

<https://trello.com/b/6sKUhdUz/openaire-explore>

This factsheet is also available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1078790>

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Useful Links

EXPLORE Discovery Portal <https://explore.openaire.eu>

Guides

Link ORCID scholarly works in OpenAIRE EXPLORE

<https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-explore-integration-with-the-orcid-search-and-link-wizard>

EXPLORE - How to report your publication and data to the EC

<https://www.openaire.eu/reporting-to-the-ec>

EXPLORE - How to link a publication to your funding

<https://www.openaire.eu/claim-publication>

Articles

New Funders page added to OpenAIRE EXPLORE!

<https://www.openaire.eu/new-funders-page-added-to-openaire-explore>

OpenAIRE EXPLORE: Introducing Sustainable Development Goals and Fields of Science classifications

<https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-explore-introducing-sdgs-and-fos>

EXPLORE: Search Open Science scholarly works

<https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/explore-search-open-science-scholarly-works>